

ATTITUDE OF REGULAR TEACHERS TOWARDS INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN PORT HARCOURT METROPOLIS, RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study investigated the attitude of regular teachers towards inclusive education in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The study employed a descriptive research approach. To direct the investigation, two null hypotheses and two research questions were developed. The survey encompassed all 678 regular instructors employed by 52 public secondary schools. A stratified random sampling technique was used to select a sample of 362 respondents for the study. A self-designed questionnaire titled: 'Regular Teachers Attitude and Inclusive Education Questionnaire' (RTAIEQ) was used for data collection. The reliability coefficient for (RTAIEQ) was $r=0.79$. To address the study issues, the mean and standard deviation were employed, and the independent sample t-test was utilized to examine the null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. The study concluded that; economic status and gender did not significantly influence the attitude of regular teachers towards inclusive education. It was recommended among others that; irrespective of the social and economic strata, regular school teachers should be encouraged to participate in workshops and seminars that will enhance their knowledge of the practice of inclusion and ultimately boost their desire to practice inclusion.

Keywords: Teachers' attitude; Inclusive education; Regular teachers; Impairments

Introduction

Attitude is the key to learning. It characterizes a person's disposition, viewpoint, or response to an object, activity, person, or thing—whether it be alive or inanimate. Grane (2016) defines attitude as a person's evaluation of a certain subject, whether positive or negative. According to the aforementioned observation, teachers' attitudes toward students who have hearing impairments may be defined as their favorable or unfavorable attitude or view of these students. Numerous studies have shown that educators have negative views about students with impairments and never value the idea of including them in normal education sessions. Compared to students with mental disabilities or hearing impairments, teachers tended to be more accepting of students with autism (Halla, 2018).

Similarly, a psychological propensity that shows itself as a level of favouring or disfavoritism toward a certain thing is what Kinanee and Ubani (2020) define as attitude. The three types of triangulating factors are the: cognitive, which consists of your ideas and beliefs about the subject; behavioural, which establishes how your behaviour is influenced by your attitude; and emotional, which expresses how you feel about the thing, person, issue, or event. Teachers have an impact on the attitudes of their students as well as their learning outcomes. Instructor attitudes have the potential to either significantly aid or hinder students with hearing problems. Under their direction, students with hearing impairments progress academically and socially inside the school system as teachers are seen as middlemen in the rehabilitation process (Halla, 2018).

Over the past thirty years, there has been a global conversation on inclusive education, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria. In the same classroom, that is, for students with and without disabilities. During the conversation, opinions for and against inclusive education were expressed. According to Ubani and Sanikpege (2020), among others, inclusive education is the most effective means of eradicating discriminatory mindsets,

promoting inclusive communities, building an inclusive society, and ensuring that all students have equitable access to formal education. According to Ubani et al. (2019), the philosophy and practices used to teach students with disabilities in conventional classroom environments are referred to as inclusive education. The idea that each kid should be treated equally as a part of the school community serves as the foundation for the practice. Put another way, students with disabilities gain by attending regular classrooms, while classmates without disabilities benefit from being among kids with different traits, skills, and personalities. According to Ajuwon (2018), proponents of inclusive education describe the term as a commitment to teach all children in the classroom and school that they would typically attend, to the maximum degree that is appropriate. All that is required is for the child to benefit from attending the class instead of having to stay up late with the other students. It means giving the child the supplementary services. This is an essential element of inclusion that requires a commitment to providing the impaired child with the resources they need rather than placing them in a remote area where services are provided (Smith, 2017; Ubani et al, 2019).

General education teachers must be capable of teaching a wider range of students, including those with various disabilities, and collaborating well with special educators during the planning process if they wish the student with a disability to gain as much as possible from inclusive education. Many countries, both developed and developing, widely implement inclusive education within their educational systems. Nigeria has adopted the inclusive education principle in its National Policy on Education. Under the initiative, students with special needs must be incorporated into regular courses, and exceptional students at all levels must get free education (Ubani, 2022).

Ajuwon (2018) adduces the evident advantages of the inclusive education paradigm, namely that children are more likely to acquire social skills in a setting that closely resembles typical growth and development settings. According to Brown (2015), children who spend their early years with other children who talk correctly and normally help them acquire language skills more successfully. It is frequently satisfying to see that children and teenagers with physical impairments can operate better than they would in non-accessible classroom and community situations, both physically and programmatically. Moreover, it is clear that these alterations to the surroundings frequently make it easier for people without impairments to access their surroundings (Ferguson, 2016).

Not only does environmental accessibility demand special attention, inclusive education has been increasingly popular in the last several years. This is partially because of how regular teachers feel about the exercise. These subjects have been studied because of the 'National Policy on Education' which outlines the problems with equity and inclusive education, especially about the rights of children with exceptionality and those without disabilities to education. Before this, there was a highly dehumanizing and negative attitude toward children with exceptionality in the public, government, and society. It was believed that people with impairments couldn't contribute anything to society.

An essential quality of the individual known as a teacher is their "attitude." Many things influence his productivity, such as how he or she feels about work, students, and many other facets of life. This evaluation, which was completed by a teacher who could have been reacting to the new inclusive policy at his school or working with students who had received an impairment diagnosis, encapsulates the typical sentiment of modern educators regarding this paradigm shift in educational policy. Harkens (2017) asserts that the instructor's reply reveals a strong view on two things: first, the academic status of the students in his class who have special needs, and second, the amount of effort he is willing to do as their teacher. The integration of previously separated pupils into general education classrooms can be thwarted from the start by any of these mindsets, which can have a significant influence on teaching methods.

The essence of the teacher's views on his students is embodied in his division of the class into two groups: those who "can learn something" and, more subtly, "those who cannot." This particular assessment, perhaps because of

their negative opinions of the exceptional children, is not new; rather, Nigerian educators and administrators have used it repeatedly throughout the 20th and 21st centuries as a rationale for refusing educational opportunities to those who are judged "in educable." In another case, a child was declared "mentally retarded," which meant he was incapable of learning, and as a result, he was not allowed to enroll in school. The Nigerian instructors of that era felt that sending special needs children to school was a complete waste of time since they could not fit into the regular system and learn with just the tools and supports available to "normal" students. Consequently, a number of these teacher decisions have negatively impacted the education of special needs children, resulting in problems with their academic performance. Thus, the a need to examine regular teachers' attitudes toward inclusive education.

Statement of the Problem

Over time, there has been an increasing disparity in educational accessibility between children who do not have disabilities and children who are developing normally. Even while inclusive education typically has numerous benefits, several obstacles keep it from being applied successfully. If inclusive education fails, it might lead to discrimination, segregation, and unfair comparisons based on superiority and inferiority. Inclusive education is the process of improving a country's educational system so that it can interact with a diverse variety of learners. Inclusive education is based on the idea that children with special needs should have the same access to general education as their counterparts without disabilities, provided they can benefit from necessary modifications and support throughout their time in school.

Several barriers prevent inclusive education programs from being implemented successfully in many nations, even in those where there are strong regulations regarding the matter. The people responsible for implementing inclusive education may not see it positively even if inclusive education is effectively advocated for. The negative opinions of stakeholders, especially regular teachers, may be a significant obstacle to inclusive education. With the correct attitude, normal instructors may help children with exceptionalities effectively transition into regular classes. Schools may be able to establish more inclusive learning environments if their employees have positive attitudes. The study therefore investigated attitude of regular teachers towards inclusive education.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to investigate attitude of regular teachers towards inclusive education in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State, Nigeria. In particular, the study objectives were to:

1. ascertain the attitude of regular teachers towards inclusive education based on economic status
2. find out the attitude of regular teachers towards inclusive education based on gender

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study.

1. To what extent does economic status influence the attitude of regular teachers towards inclusive education?
2. To what extent does gender influence the attitude of regular teachers towards inclusive education?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of high and low economic status teachers on their attitude towards inclusive education
2. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on their attitude towards inclusive education

Method

The study employed a descriptive research approach. The survey encompassed all 678 regular instructors employed by 52 public secondary schools. Stratified random sampling technique was used to select a sample of 362 respondents for the study. Stratified random sampling technique was adopted to select a target population of 362 regular instructors in the region's public secondary schools. The research instrument was a self-designed instrument titled: "Regular Teachers Attitude and Inclusive Education Questionnaire" (RTAIEQ). Section A included the respondents' demographic information whereas Section B was designed using a modified four-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) respectively. Section B had a total of 25 items. The reliability coefficient of (RTAIEQ) was $r=0.79$ and was determined using the test-retest method. The independent t-test was employed to examine the null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance, and the research questions were addressed utilizing the mean and standard deviation.

Research Question One: To what extent does economic status influence the attitude of regular teachers towards inclusive education?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation showing the extent economic status influence the attitude of regular teachers towards inclusive education

S/N	Item	High N=160		Low N=202	
		X	SD	X	SD
1	Teaching experience improves teachers' attitude toward inclusion.	2.51	0.87	2.03	0.75
2	Teacher knowledge about inclusion play important role in the implementation of inclusive education.	2.75	0.73	3.20	0.99
3	Positive attitude of teacher contributes to meet the need of inclusive education.	2.36	0.66	3.19	0.58
4	You feel motivated when teaching in an inclusive school.	3.02	0.15	2.83	1.31
5	Lack of learning material contributes to teachers' negative attitude towards inclusive education.	2.10	0.92	3.97	0.84
6	Teachers' academic background influence teachers' attitude towards inclusive education.	2.70	0.54	3.98	0.73
7	Teachers are considered as main factor that influences the success of inclusive education.	2.92	0.64	3.14	0.76
8	Positive attitude of teachers contribute to the successful implementation of inclusive education	2.56	0.94	3.41	1.41
9	Teachers' views and attitude towards inclusion are as important as the implementation of inclusive education.	2.84	0.57	2.77	0.41
10	The effectiveness of inclusive education depends on teachers' attitude and implementation.	2.88	0.10	2.67	0.57
11	Teachers are the driving force behind inclusive education.	2.77	0.66	3.07	0.96
12	Lack of self-confidence of teacher hinders effective implementation of inclusive education.	3.87	0.72	2.51	0.54
13	Teachers' voices and opinion are very important inclusion issues.	3.10	0.90	3.01	0.81
14	Government are the major causes of the failure of inclusive education.	2.77	0.86	3.49	0.66
15	Negative attitude of teachers limit students with special need and prevent responsibility for their success.	2.72	0.12	2.27	0.72
16	Level of professional training help teacher to perform better in an inclusive	2.15	0.77	2.30	0.90

	education.								
17	Lack of accessible and flexible curriculum are the main challenges to negative attitude among teachers for an inclusive education setting.	2.87	0.70	3.48	0.94				
18	Teachers with positive attitude find it easier to work in an inclusive education setting.	2.70	0.90	3.11	0.22				
19	One of the obstacles to inclusive education is said to be the shortage of special education instructors with the necessary training.	2.18	1.00	2.58	0.80				
20	Adequate teachers training is absolutely vital to provide high quality education in an inclusive education.	3.09	0.98	3.02	0.15				
21	Pre-service training for teachers in an inclusive education would help guarantee successful inclusion.	3.19	0.90	3.33	0.85				
22	Providing pre-service professional development lead to positive attitude of teachers towards inclusion.	3.16	0.92	2.52	0.45				
23	Many teachers lack knowledge and skill to teacher in an inclusive education setting.	3.21	0.56	2.01	0.70				
24	Teachers having negative attitude towards inclusive education will not have satisfaction in classroom.	3.40	0.93	3.99	0.32				
25	Teachers positive attitude play a key role in the success of social interaction between teachers and student in an inclusive setting	3.00	0.45	3.67	0.55				
Grand Mean/SD		3.33	0.35	3.19	0.83				

Table 1 shows the extent economic status influence the attitude of regular teachers towards inclusive education. Specifically the result indicates that the grand mean for teachers with HES as ($X=3.33;SD=0.35$), and (teachers with LES as $X=3.19;SD=0.83$) which is below the >2.50 threshold mean. This further indicates that economic status positively influence the attitude of regular teachers towards inclusive education.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of high and low economic status teachers on their attitude towards inclusive education

Table 2: T-test analysis showing significant difference in the mean rating of high and low economic status teachers on their attitude towards inclusive education

Economic Status	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	Sig.	Remark
High	160	2.33	0.35	360	0.000	Significant.
Low	202	2.19	0.83			

According to Table 2, the P-value is 0.000 and at 360 degrees of freedom. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of high and low economic status teachers on their attitude towards inclusive education is rejected.

Research Question Two: To what extent does gender influence the attitude of regular teachers towards inclusive education?

Table 4.3: Mean and standard deviation showing the extent gender influence the attitude of regular teachers towards inclusive education

S/N	Item	Male N=170		Female N=192	
		X	SD	X	SD
1	Teaching experience improves teachers' attitude toward inclusion.	2.18	0.56	2.11	0.93
2	Teacher knowledge about inclusion play important role in the implementation of inclusive education.	2.31	0.77	2.33	0.93
3	Positive attitude of teacher contributes to meet the need of inclusive education.	1.89	0.98	2.71	0.43
4	You feel motivated when teaching in an inclusive school.	2.02	0.81	2.04	0.88
5	Lack of learning material contributes to teachers' negative attitude towards inclusive education.	1.36	0.70	2.00	0.94
6	Teachers' academic background influence teachers' attitude towards inclusive education.	1.72	0.60	2.07	0.10
7	Teachers are considered as main factor that influences the success of inclusive education.	1.74	0.58	1.79	0.90
8	Positive attitude of teachers contribute to the successful implementation of inclusive education.	2.01	0.90	2.06	0.40
9	Teachers' views and attitude towards inclusion are as important as the implementation of inclusive education.	1.20	0.77	1.92	0.21
10	The effectiveness of inclusive education depends on teachers' attitude and implementation.	2.34	0.10	1.86	0.91
11	Teachers are the driving force behind inclusive education.	2.01	0.87	2.03	0.75
12	Lack of self-confidence of teacher hinders effective implementation of inclusive education.	2.15	0.73	1.20	0.99
13	Teachers' voices and opinion are very important inclusion issues.	2.36	0.66	1.19	0.58
14	Government are the major causes of the failure of inclusive education.	2.02	0.15	1.83	0.31
15	Negative attitude of teachers limit students with special need and prevent responsibility for their success.	1.99	0.66	1.86	0.91
16	Level of professional training help teacher to perform better in an inclusive education.	2.10	0.92	1.97	0.84
17	Lack of accessible and flexible curriculum are the main challenges to negative attitude among teachers for an inclusive education setting.	2.00	0.54	1.98	0.73
18	Teachers with positive attitude find it easier to work in an inclusive education setting.	1.92	0.64	2.14	0.76
19	One of the obstacles to inclusive education is said to be the shortage of special education instructors with the necessary training.	2.56	0.94	1.91	0.41
20	Adequate teachers training is absolutely vital to provide high quality education in an inclusive education.	1.74	0.47	1.77	0.41
21	Pre-service training for teachers in an inclusive education would help guarantee successful inclusion.	1.88	0.40	1.67	0.57
22	Providing pre-service professional development lead to positive attitude of teachers towards inclusion.	2.10	0.60	1.97	0.90
23	Many teachers lack knowledge and skill to teacher in an inclusive education setting.	2.37	0.10	1.95	0.55

24	Teachers having negative attitude towards inclusive education will not have satisfaction in classroom.	2.00	0.80	1.59	0.70
25	Teachers positive attitude play a key role in the success of social interaction between teachers and student in an inclusive setting	2.01	0.34	2.00	0.49
Grand Mean/SD		2.00	0.54	2.33	0.81

Table 3 shows the extent gender influence the attitude of regular teachers towards inclusive education. Specifically the result indicates that the grand mean for male teachers as ($X=2.00;SD=0.54$), and (female teachers as $X=2.33;SD=0.81$) which is below the >2.50 threshold mean. This further indicates that gender does not positively influence the attitude of regular teachers towards inclusive education.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on their attitude towards inclusive education

Table 4: T-test analysis showing significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on their attitude towards inclusive education

Gender	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	Critical t-value	Remark
Male	170	2.00	0.54	360	0.073	Not Significant.
Female	192	2.33	0.81			

Table 4 shows that the P-value is 0.073 and at 360 degrees of freedom. Since the P-value (0.073) is higher than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on their attitude towards inclusive education is accepted.

Discussion of the Findings

The results of the first study question (Table 1) and hypothesis (Table 2) showed that there is positive influence of economic status on the attitude of regular teachers towards inclusive education. And that there is significant difference in the mean rating of high and low economic status teachers on their attitude towards inclusive education. The finding are contrary to the study of Baar (2016) writing on “Attitude of German student teachers on inclusion” found that student instructors' favorable attitudes about inclusiveness were unaffected by their socioeconomic status. The research findings are consistent with Cronin's (2017) research on the views of rural teachers, administrators, and counsellors toward inclusive education. Cronin argued that social and economic strength were among the many positive variables that positively impacted inclusive education.

The results of the second study question (Table 3) and hypothesis (Table 4) showed that there is positive influence of gender on the attitude of regular teachers towards inclusive education. And that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female teachers on their attitude towards inclusive education. The results are consistent with the findings of Ubani and Sanikpege (2023), who wrote on "Barriers globally faced by persons with disabilities." They noted that the Ghanaian educational system generally promotes the idea of inclusive education and that teachers' and stakeholders' genders had no positive impact on their attitudes toward inclusive educational practices.

Conclusion

The study's results led the researcher to the conclusion that economic status and gender did not significantly influenced regular educators' perspectives on inclusive education in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

Recommendation

1. Regardless of social or economic background, ordinary school teachers ought to be motivated to attend workshops and seminars that will broaden their understanding of inclusionary practices and, in turn, increase their motivation to implement inclusive practices.
2. In addition, it is advised that administrators and regular instructors in inclusive schools be prepared to act as loco parentis toward pupils with and without impairments, regardless of gender.

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